

MARKETING OPPORTUNITIES ON DEVELOPING TOURISM

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ANNOTATION

In the article, importance of marketing in tourism and several ways of developing tourism by marketing are explained. Also recommendations are presented for companies which based on touristic services.

Key words: *Tourism, distination, product, customer, consumer,marketer, Strategy.*

Tourism is the departure (travel) of an individual from the place of permanent residence for a long period of one year without engaging in paid activities in the destination (country) for health, educational, professional-practical or other purposes. . The application of marketing in the field of tourism is to produce a special tourist product in the market and direct it to a specific consumer. is related to the development of a strategy for increasing sales and choosing the 406 most effective means of advertising information. The movement of tourist services to the consumer is not carried out directly. In this way, tourist services become tourist products through tour operators and distribution system, i.e. tourist agencies, and reach the consumer. In general, the complex of activities from the development of tourist services to the consumer reflects the marketing complex. About the importance of tourism marketing, American expert G. Harris says the following: "Tourism does not need simple marketing. It should be able to make the steps more attractive. This means preservation and beautification of the natural tourist object. In the end, unique cultural heritage, wild nature or beautiful landscape attract tourists in the first place. This definition shows the

role of the state in tourism marketing. The World Tourism Organization (WTO) distinguishes three functions of tourism marketing: contact with customers, development and control. The main purpose of customer communication is to convince the customer that the proposed trips meet the full standards. The development function consists of introducing innovations into the system to further improve the service and meet customer demand. The control function means the analysis of the level of tourist services and the quality of the tourism market.

Tourism marketing consists of systematic and unified actions of national tourism organizations or tourism institutions, depending on the satisfaction (optimization) of the needs of tourists at the national and international level. In order to appreciate people's free time, the desire and need to travel in a region, country or between countries for the purpose of work, family, conference, caused the establishment of tourist enterprises. These enterprises are creating a number of methods and techniques in order to make tourist groups, who are consumers, travel in the most suitable places and in the best conditions. Marketing is an ongoing process. Tourist products and services are sold directly to tourists by tourist enterprises or through intermediary firms, travel agencies or tour operators. In tourism marketing, new needs of tourists should be continuously searched and studied. The needs of the traveler come first.

Tourism marketing is simply any marketing strategy used by businesses within the tourism industry. This includes, for example, hotels and other forms of accommodation, along with airlines, car rental services, restaurants, entertainment venues, travel agents and tour operators. Like any other marketing activity, the purpose of tourism marketing is to promote the business, make it stand out from rivals, attract customers, and generate brand awareness. Digital channels such as social media, search engine marketing, etc. Traditional channels like printed ads, billboards, radio, or TV.

Tourism marketing is not only for companies and businesses operating in the industry. On a state level nations compete with each other to get the biggest share of visitors. They utilize tourism marketing to create a "country brand". A country brand is the intangible characteristics and associations that people relate to the name of the

country. Paris is the city of light, entertainment, fashion, and nightlife. Thailand is known for its paradise-like islands.

People love to talk about their travels. Especially if the place is exotic or far away from their home country. If visitors are recommending the country to their friends and relatives, their experience must have been positive.

The main purpose of customer communication is to convince the customer that the proposed trips meet the full standards. The development function consists of introducing innovations into the system to further improve the service and meet customer demand. The control function means the analysis of the level of tourist services and the quality of the tourism market. Renting car or booking a hotel stay does not require much innovation. Two hotels may be in the same location and have the same facilities, but one of them could be making more profit than the other. What differentiates a service is creating a familiar, cosy atmosphere. Guests, visitors and users like that feeling of familiarity; the feeling of being home. They want the same comfortable car they have tried before, the same clean and sunny room they stayed in last time. That's not the case with product marketing where consumers are continuously looking for new experiences. The important characteristics of tourism compared to other products or services make the use of marketing in this area very necessary. The tourism product, unlike other goods and services, has the characteristics of a mixed product that is finished compared to other institutions. Tourist demand for tourism products is also sensitive to social and political changes and shows great elasticity.

Customers want to know about products and services in a pertinent and time-sensitive manner; too much information and selling can be off-putting for them. A knowledge base is a great way to provide existing customers with the information they

need when they need it. Now, in such a transforming around the-clock industry, customers are confused. They need simple and direct answer.

One the biggest mistakes that tourism marketers make is ‘yelling at’ clients with services rather than ‘speaking with’ the customer about the functional benefits and emotional benefits. Watch half an hour of TV one night and you will see brand after brand yelling service after service after service. This type of tourism marketing just forces the consumer to have to figure out what they get from your brand. In crowded market, where your potential clients are chased around by 7000 brand messages per day, you have just lost out on the oppirtunity to find a set of customer- oriented benefits that your brand can use to motivate them instead of owning these benefits as you build the reputation of your brand.

Let’s devide marketing strategies on developing business, we’ll cover the five elements you need to create a tourism marketing strategy. You can tailor each step to your brand to help you stand out from the competition.

1. A mobile-responsive website
2. An email marketing tool
3. A primary social media channel
4. Up-to-date business listings
5. A way to easily create content

Tourism development cannot be imagined without marketing. Because marketing plays a key role in studying the tourism market. However, marketing services are not well established in the tourism system of our republic. For this, it is necessary to study foreign tourist markets and try to sell national tourist products there. Currently, the price policy cannot be called good, even if the demand for our national products is at an average level. Prices are very high compared to products from the world market. Therefore, the demand of tourists is decreasing. They are visiting for organizational purposes only.

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